

FIELDS

Mathematics Education Forum

January 25, 2025, 09:55 AM – 2:35 PM ET

Fields Institute, 222 College Street, Toronto

Tweet us @FieldsMathEd

Research Day 2025

Organizers: Steven Khan (Brock University) and Ami Mamolo (Ontario Tech University)

9:55 AM - 10:05 AM Welcome to the Forum

Description: In person and online participants arrive and are welcomed. All participants are present for the land acknowledgement and are introduced to the program of the day.

10:05 AM - 10:10 AM Reports from OAME, OMCA, OCMA, OCMC, CMESG, CMS, CME, FYMSiC, AFEMO, and others.

10:10 AM – 11:00 AM

KEYNOTE

Scientific orientations, examples and findings of a research programme in mental mathematics

Jérôme Proulx (Université du Québec à Montréal)

Abstract. In this Research Keynote presentation, I present the general scientific orientations of our research lab, leading to specific ones about my current research programme focused on mental mathematics. In so doing, examples will be given of tasks used and of students' ways of engaging with these. These various examples of tasks and students' strategies are used throughout the presentation to explain the nature of the findings developed in this research programme, and make concrete underlying conceptualisations about students' strategy processes in mental mathematics environments.

Bio. Jérôme Proulx is a professor of mathematics education (*didactique des mathématiques* : www.profmath.uqam.ca/~jproulx), and runs the Laboratoire Épistémologie et Activité Mathématique (www.lead.uqam.ca). His research focuses on epistemological issues related to cognition and/in mathematics. His current research programme is dedicated to mental mathematics and school mathematics content development.

11:15 AM – 11:45 AM

RESEARCH SNAPSHOTS

11:00 - 11:15

Potential for Integrating Modeling in CÉGEP to Develop Critical Thinking

Shophika Vaithyanathasarma (Boston College)

Abstract. This exploratory study studies the potential of mathematical modeling to include Calculus courses as contributors to the development of critical thinking among students. To do this, we conducted semi-directed interviews with 8 teachers in whom we sought to identify their relationship (Therriault, 2008) to mathematics, critical thinking and mathematical

modeling knowledges. During a second meeting, we had them try a modeling activity of their choice from those offered on the Via Math website. Through the data collected, we were able to first identify benefits and limitations related to the integration of modeling into teaching practice. Then, we were able to identify associations between modeling phases (Caron, 2008) and critical thinking competencies (Heard et al., 2020). The results show that mathematical modeling, in principle, promotes the development of critical thinking. In addition, it allows mathematical concepts to be contextualized in real situations, thus strengthening student engagement and their ability to establish interdisciplinary connections. However, integrating mathematical modeling into teaching presents challenges. Teachers express limited comfort with modeling phases and critical thinking skills, highlighting particular difficulties in mathematization and mathematical processing. Some mentioned a lack of specific training in modeling and a lack of time related to the prescribed content to be covered in class. Despite these challenges, teachers recognize critical thinking as an important skill to develop across their discipline and remain open to integrating approaches into their teaching that promote a conceptual understanding of mathematics.

11:15 - 11:30

Evaluation of Mathematics Interventions: Propensity score analysis as an alternative to randomized control

Andrew Arizaga and Francis Duah (Toronto Metropolitan University)

Abstract. Many first-year students find the transition to post-secondary mathematics education challenging. Toronto Metropolitan University (TMU), like many other institutions, has implemented several intervention programs to address the knowledge gap of first year students or provide support for them when they transition to university mathematics. However, rigorous evaluation of similar or related programmes have always been a challenge in mathematics education research due to ethical reasons or self selection bias. Randomized control trial, which is the gold standard for scientific research, is not always feasible for evaluating interventions such as those cited in the preceding paragraph. This talk is a preliminary undergraduate thesis report in which we argue that Propensity Score Analysis (PSA) (Thoemmes and Kim, 2011) is a statistical methodology that can be employed to address the issue of self selection bias inherent in the evaluation of mathematics education intervention programmes. We use simulated data to demonstrate how the PSA procedure can be used to evaluate mathematics education interventions such as ACES. We highlight the challenges involved in the implementation of PSA. We suggest some potential reasons why PSA is not well known and used in mathematics education research. We conclude that 1) PSA is the next best alternative to randomized controlled trial and 2) there is a need for collaborative research that employs the technique and offers workshops on the implementation of PSA.

11:30 AM- 12:00 PM

KEYNOTE

Examining coloniality in mathematics education curriculum: A case of the Cambridge Assessment International Education curriculum

Molade Osibodu (York University)

Abstract. In this talk, I examine coloniality as a racializing force within mathematics education curricula, focusing on the British-developed Cambridge Assessment International Education (CAIE) curriculum, formerly known as the Cambridge International Education (CIE) curriculum. Through this case study, I explore how international curricula like CAIE operate as vehicles of coloniality, embedding and perpetuating racialized narratives about Sub-Saharan African communities. I argue that CAIE plays a central role in sustaining colonial hierarchies by privileging a singular, Eurocentric way of knowing and being in mathematics. These hierarchies are further reinforced through the curriculum's assessment practices, which not only marginalize alternative epistemologies but also uphold systems of exclusion and inequality. The persistence of colonial logics in international education underscores the need to interrogate the broader power structures that shape mathematics curricula globally. By recognizing the ways in which coloniality and racialization are interconnected, we can better understand the complex systems of power and privilege that shape international mathematics curricula.

Bio. Molade Osibodu, PhD is an Assistant Professor of Mathematics Education at York University located in Toronto, Ontario, Canada. Her research critically examines the experiences of Black youth in mathematics education. Dr. Osibodu is specifically interested in examining ways to decolonize mathematics education for liberatory futures, engaging with social justice issues, and exploring African Indigenous mathematics practices. Dr. Osibodu's work is supported methodologically and theoretically by decolonial theory, critical theories of race, and Black geographies.

12:00 PM – 12:55 PM

LUNCH BREAK

(Light refreshments provided)

12:30 PM – 1:15 PM

POSTER PRESENTATIONS

1. *Double the Productivity: Distinguishing Struggle and Failure*
Andrew Divito & Robyn Ruttenberg-Rozen (Ontario Tech University)
2. *The Role of Composition, De-composition, and Comparison Activities in 3- and 4-Year Old Children's Abstraction Processes in Shape Recognition*
Ayse Pinar Sen (Brock University)
3. *Enhancing Novice Tutors' Confidence and K-8 Student Outcomes in After-School Math Support*
Catherine Susin & Isabella Favero (Brock University)
4. *The Decimal Manipulative: A New Tool to Teach Decimals*
Connor Bradey (Upper Grand DSB & Waterloo Region DSB)
5. *Leveraging Teacher Agency Through STEM Learning in the Early Year Classroom*
Jennifer Muchmaker & Robyn Ruttenberg-Rozen (Ontario Tech University)
6. *Big Stories in Small Spirals: Exploring how Teachers Conceptualize and Enact a Spiralled Curriculum in Grade 9 Ontario Mathematics Classrooms*
Mena Fahmi (University of Ottawa)
7. *PSTS Design of Data Visualizations: Tensions and Intentions*
Nkechi Ibeh & Ami Mamolo (Ontario Tech University)
8. *Research on Mathematics Interventions for Young Children with Autism*
Olivia Conway Jenner & Robyn Ruttenberg-Rozen (Ontario Tech University)
9. *Examples Presented in Calculus Textbooks: Differences or Otherwise Between Commercial Textbooks and Open Educational Resource Textbooks*
Serban Boghina & Francis Duah (Toronto Metropolitan University)
10. *Teacher-Researcher Autoethnography of a Secondary School Teacher Attempting to Conduct Action Research in a Destreamed Mathematics Classroom*
Steven Roach (Niagara Catholic District School Board)
11. *Evaluating the Association Between Attitudes Toward Mathematics and Mathematics Achievements Using Multilevel Modeling: Comparing TIMSS 2019 scores in Ontario and Quebec Fourth and Eighth Grade Students*
Sylvia Langton & Dragana Martinovic (University of Windsor)

1:15 PM – 1:45 PM

RESEARCH SNAPSHOTS

1:15 PM - 1:30 PM

Development of a Parent-Teacher Co-Teaching Framework to Address Contemporary Challenges in Mathematics Education

Awa Ndiaye (University of Ottawa)

Abstract. In response to contemporary challenges in mathematics education, such as student disengagement (Shabab, 2024; Skilling and al., 2021) and equity issues (Cai et al., 2020), this research builds on a pilot project, "Parent partenaire en enseignement" (2022-2023). Conducted in a Franco-Ontarian school, the project involved 80 students, 8 parents, and school administrators in co-teaching experiences to improve student achievement and social-emotional learning (SEL) skills, as emphasized in Ontario's revised mathematics curriculum (OME, 2020). The co-teaching model, structured around the phases of co-planning, co-instruction, and co-evaluation (Harent, 2023), explored the potential of parental involvement in mathematics education. This research addresses three primary questions: How can structured parent-teacher co-teaching in mathematics enhance student engagement and academic achievement, particularly for diverse and marginalized students? What are the key components of an effective co-teaching framework that integrates parents into formal mathematics instruction? How does co-teaching influence the development of students' SEL skills, and how does it impact equity in mathematics education? Preliminary findings from the pilot suggest that parent involvement positively affects student motivation and mathematical performance, particularly for students with special needs (Sileo and Van Garderen, 2009). Additionally, co-teaching facilitated the development of SEL skills (Claus et al., 2022). This approach also strengthened school-family collaboration (Deslandes, 2019), creating a more inclusive and supportive learning environment. The ongoing research seeks to refine and validate this framework through an iterative research-development methodology (Bergeron & Rousseau, 2021), addressing challenges related to inclusion, well-being, and teacher professional development (Gardesten, 2023).

1:30 PM - 1:45 PM

Legitimizing the Other: An Enactivist Study on the Efficacy of Number Talks in Elementary Classrooms

Marc Husband, Evan Throop-Robinson, & Allison Tucker (St. Francis Xavier University).

Abstract. There is widespread uptake of Number Talks in elementary classrooms. Despite their use, there is limited research on their effectiveness in the mathematics education literature. Matney et al. (2020) describe the lack of data on teachers implementing Number Talks as a

"black hole" (p. 247), emphasizing the complexity of the practice due to five essential, rapidly occurring, components: 1. classroom environment and community, 2. classroom discourse, 3. the teacher's role in questioning and supporting student reasoning, 4. the role of mental math and 5. purposeful computation problems. Our study addresses this gap by investigating Number Talks, enacted in Nova Scotia schools across two Regional Centres for Education, through an inquiry-based professional learning project involving 16 elementary teachers. Over three full-day sessions, teachers co-planned and observed Number Talks in classrooms. The data consisted of video recordings of the Number Talks from those days. We analyzed these videos using Maturana & Varela's (1992) enactivist perspective—teacher and students acting collectively on ideas. Our research question asked: What is the efficacy of Number Talks in relation to Matney et al.'s components within the typical 12-15 minute format? Our findings suggest that Number Talks hold the potential for teachers to elicit and legitimize students' mental math strategies and for students to recognize and build on each other's ideas. This study contributes to the emerging literature by offering insights into the efficacy of Number Talks and the potential for fostering deeper mathematical thinking in short time frames.

1:45 PM - 2:00 PM

Open Discussion

2:00 PM - 2:30 PM

POSTER PRESENTATIONS CONT'D

2:00 PM - ADJOURNMENT OF ONLINE PROGRAM

2:30 PM - ADJOURNMENT OF IN-PERSON PROGRAM